

Designing for body, mind and context. *Values-in-action* to bridge design and business.

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Abstract

Design affects us immensely in how we behave, think and feel. Yet it remains a challenge to make conscious design decisions in the development processes of products that reflect the responsibility we thus bear. Trying to illuminate aspects of how we through design interfere with end-users rational and emotional worlds and can deal with that challenge, I have become interested in the notion of *values*. In this paper I will use three kitchen design cases to explore the notion of end-user values for design practice. The experience from these cases is conferred with literature from marketing and a user-centered and interaction design perspective. To make fundamental distinctions, I take a cross-disciplinary stance, which draws on a social constructionist rather than a business perspective, yet acknowledges advantages of the latter. I exemplify the discrepancies between value, as *e-value*-ation of design and discovering family and kitchen life values through user involvement in a mixed-methods approach, which was employed in the main design case discusses here, the prototyping project. Bringing back the focus from process to design outcome and effect, I address two small design cases of redesigning the microwave oven. I finally propose the *values-in-action* notion to bridge disciplinary cultures and help take conscious design decisions.

Conference theme: Values and Culture

Keywords: Values, context, interaction.

How *value* challenges design practice

An ever-prominent challenge for designers, in the course of designing, is to anticipate actual use of a product, before it is put on the market. This becomes especially apparent as we consider how computing increasingly is becoming embedded in the physical world around us. As Harper, Rodden, Rogers and Sellen describe, our future challenge is “to understand and design for interaction in a world where the notion of an interface is no longer easily defined” (Harper, Rodden, Rogers, Sellen, 2008, p.36). So contexts are becoming more and more complex, as well

as the products themselves, which then require to be developed in coordination with a range of professional disciplines. Along the lines of the vast possibilities, which the unbroken advancement of technologies allows, we need ways to navigate this world of design choices. User-centered design proposes strategies and methods to tackle this challenge by an early and continuous involvement of the end-users in the design process. As Buur and Ylirisku put it:

User-centered design promotes the understanding of the use context. Designs are perceived as good or bad in relation to how well they fit to the users, their aspirations and their ways of going about things. Knowing a future “well enough” thus presumes developing an understanding about how the proposed designs function in the active world of the users. (Buur & Ylirisku, 2007, p.174)

This younger discipline however tends to clash with other, by industry more acknowledged traditions, such as marketing that as well has its methods and makes some claim on consumer knowledge. If we look at marketing as a somewhat comparable competition to user-centered design, it has the advantage of being widely embedded in company landscapes, whereas the user-centered design approach is more contextual and links directly to design practice. Yet, instead of fighting each other, I want to ask: What can we learn from each other? There has long been a need for user-centered design to better understand how to integrate with the business agenda of companies, while one can suggest this being a mutual challenge. To partly explore this, I here put forward *value/s* as a potential bridge between the business domain, specifically marketing, and the design domain. Beyond user-centered design that is more focused on process and designing for fit, we also need to consider how interaction design can contribute to the innovative interfaces of the future.

Why this is important

Current developments within the human computer interaction (HCI) field recognize and suggest that “ ‘being human’ in our relationship with technology means that we need to bring to the fore and better understand human values and make them central to how we understand and design for a changing world” (Harper, Rodden, Rogers, Sellen, 2008, p.35). Dealing with the term *value*, its underlying meanings and how we may utilize this is however far more complicated. The ambiguity of the value-term can create many misunderstandings in a design process. At the same time its widespread use, also across disciplines, makes it interesting and allows us to investigate how design practice can benefit from the different perspectives on the topic.

Graeber identifies three main streams of thought considering a specific notion of value: (1) *values* as “in the sociological sense: conceptions of what is ultimately good, proper, or desirable

in human life”, (2) *value* “in the linguistic sense...as meaningful difference” and (3) *value* “in the economic sense: the degree to which objects are desired, particularly, as measured by how much others are willing to give up to get them” (Graeber, 2001, pp.1-2). There have been attempts in the HCI field to deal consciously with human values in designing. With the value-sensitive design approach Friedman et. al. propose a focus on moral values, e.g. autonomy of users, to understand how technologies might undermine or support those (Friedman, 1996 & Friedman, Kahn, 2000 & Friedman, Freier 2005). Yet we need to move beyond just moral values in general. Volda and Mynatt put forward the relevance of context with their study dealing with value elicitation in the domestic sphere. Their research agenda was to “emphasize foregrounding the values of specific user populations and allowing their values to seed the design process” (Volda, Mynatt, 2005, p.2014). This puts the specific use context into play.

My starting-point is that two views on the notion of end-users value seem mostly interesting for a user-centered and interaction design perspective: (1) Human values that people in a way possess – we want to design *for* people, hence consciously deal with the design’s potential effect on people’s doing and thinking and (2) values communicated through, or somehow designed into the products of tomorrow – we want to design cues of use *into* products, in order to better anticipate use. The partition in these two views is here based on tendencies of how *value* is used in ordinary language and in multidisciplinary work, experienced in the main design case of this paper.

This paper has two main goals, to (1) develop a better *understanding* of the end-user value notion and to (2) suggest ways to *utilize* this understanding through methods and mind-set. I explore this with a cross-disciplinary perspective, mainly drawing on marketing and a social constructivist view. I then further discuss this with three examples of design projects from the kitchen context, which shed different lights on the topic. Precisely, the main case, the prototyping project Kitchen Guide, here elevates the discussion on methods of inquiry. Two student project examples of explorative microwave oven concepts briefly serve as a complementation and a critical pointer to interaction design as they highlight the actual design solutions more. Eventually I bring forward the notion of *values-in-action* to guide designers in the ways they generally think about users, investigate into their context, and finally propose a specific (interaction) design, based on an anticipated use of the product, system or service.

Fundamentally different notions of *value* - User benefits to equate value?

Value and *values* are typical marketing terms and central to the marketing concept. From a marketing perspective the end-users are the customers, whose needs are to be discovered and

satisfied (Berkowitz, Hartley, Kerin, Rudelius, 2000, p. 9 & Kotler, 2000, p.11). To do so marketing suggests mapping out customer values to base decisions on how to stand out from their competition. So one way that marketing uses the term value is as in *values people have*. Kotler refers to a customer-centered three-step process, proposed by Crego and Schiffring, in order to exceed the consumers' expectations: The first step is to "*define the customer value model*"; to list factors of product and service that could impact on the customers' perception of value. Second step is "*building the customer value hierarchy*"; the before identified factors are assigned according to basic, expected, desired and unanticipated values. Finally, the third step is "*deciding on customer value package*"; the company chooses a specific set of "items, experiences, and outcomes designed to outperform the competitors and win the customers' delight and loyalty" (Kotler, 2000, p. 286). This treats *values people have* as stable entities that one can identify, sort and manipulate consciously.

To position oneself in the industry a company can choose the strategy of differentiation "as the act of designing a set of meaningful differences to distinguish the company's offering from competitors' offerings" (Kotler, 2000, p.287). The here included product differentiation strategy directly appoints a role to design in integrating "the totality of features that affect how a product looks and functions in terms of customer requirements". The elements Kotler identifies as designable are form, features, performance, conformance, durability, reliability and style (Kotler, 2000, p.291). Without dealing with these in depth, this list however shows that interaction supposedly is not part of the designers' repertoire. Clearly interaction design exceeds this notion of the design task. Chan Kim and Mauborgne even move beyond this and suggest simply making competition irrelevant through, based on innovative product or service concepts, creating completely new markets (Chan Kim, Mauborgne, 2007). Here is the clear link to what design can contribute, namely the desired innovative concepts - in other words the desired unique value through the product. So another notion is that value can consciously be delivered to people, as it somewhat is *designed into the product*.

Furthermore it suggests that a product is successful when it delivers value and thereby satisfaction to the consumer (Kotler, 2000, p. 11). These aims would then be carried out through the process of planning and executing the marketing mix factors: product, pricing, promotion and distribution factors (Berkowitz, Hartley, Kerin, Rudelius, 2000, p. 13). So the product is only one out of several factors that are planned according to some idea of consumers' values. Based on this the company designs its product to inherit a chosen set of values – this in some way unites the idea of a *product providing value* and *people having values*. *Value for consumers*, provided by product, is more specifically equated into benefits (emotional and functional level) divided by costs (monetary, time, energy and psychic) (Kotler, 2000, p.11).

Moreover the term added value is equivalent to the term benefits. This equation of value appears static and inflexible to incorporate the richness that everyday practice entails. It further supports the general notion of values as given categories, once acknowledged we have the tendency to discuss them as fixed.

From a social constructivist perspective a product's value cannot be mirrored by a fixed value equation; hence the users do not *have* fixed and internalized values. These are instead constructed socially and highly context dependent. This is much in line with the core of user-centered design, and is further supported by theory on identity. There is not anything as one fixed identity, but a range of constantly changing, "fluid" identities relational to the social worlds we engage with [Dencik, personal communication]. As values are highly related to how we perceive ourselves, it further stresses the importance to regard values as constructed. Shotter summarizes the inevitable relational involvement of social activity as:

...through our continuous, unselfcontrolled, responsive reactions within such a flow of activity, we not only uniquely relate ourselves both to each other and to our circumstances, but, in continuing to responsively react, we also re-create such relations, continuously. (Shotter, 1996, p.5)

Interacting with products and with people through products, just as well make the objects an active participant in this continual social construction.

In summary there are two fundamentally different perspectives on end-user value for designing. One is the marketing perspective that value is a rather fixed category that can be expressed directly by its owner, and is attached to the product to satisfy the customers. This makes *value/s* graspable and therefore easier to discuss and deal with in a design process, but tends to stay superficial and loose the richness of insights that a human-centered design process intends to benefit from. The other is a social constructivist perspective that value, as part of our reality, is socially constructed in an ongoing, dynamic process in relation to the world around us. This view appears better capable to grasp the complexity of users' lives. It is therefore more suited to support design activities that thrive on those rich insights to the users' worlds.

A mixed-method approach - Family interviews about the Kitchen Guide concept

With the interviews in the Helpful Food of the Future¹ prototyping project I here want to further discuss this tension between a marketing and social constructivist type of value understanding and the usefulness of the perspectives. In the course of this project the discussion of *values*, as in *people having values* and us *providing value through design*, became significant for how to think about the involvement with and feedback of the users.

Project frames

The project was a collaboration between Innovation Lab, Århus, Denmark, five Danish food manufacturers, two IT consultancies and the Mads Clausen Institute as design and user involvement experts. The overall aims were to a) explore the potential of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology on food in the home context, and to b) explore such technology for strengthening consumers' trust in food manufacturers. The premise of the project was to deliver a functional prototype to 20 Danish families for a 2-months testing period (see figure 1 and figure 2). Weekly all families were supplied with a variation of foods with RFID-tags attached.

Figure 1: The Kitchen Guide prototype in use. As the girl scans the food she gets access to the four, interconnected, main functions.

¹ Fremtidens Hjælpssomme Mad (original Danish project title).

Figure 2: The Kitchen Guide start page that shows the main functions: *Food Magnification Glasses* (details on the specific product and contact to manufacturer), *Shopping Helper* (manage shopping away from home), *Recipe Architect* (playful generation of recipes), and *Food Planner* (plan family activities).

Limitations turned into opportunities

A main challenge was to meet the requirements of producing a functional prototype that 20 families could ‘test’ in their home. Eventually the prototype was functioning to illustrate some main ideas behind the design, yet not living up to the design concept we had in mind. So how could one ensure that the input from the families was not fully colored by frustrations with an unfinished product in order to generate relevant conclusions on the project’s goal? To avoid being limited by the prototype design we tailored the user involvement toward understanding more about the users’ worlds and how such a technological product could fit into their everyday life – eventually the underlying agenda of our inquiry. We considered the prototype not an

almost finished product to be ‘tested’, but instead as a communication trigger, a provocation for the users to support personal reflection. We attempted to elicit requirements and promising directions for such a design concept.

Shaping the family interview, to probe for added value

The main resource to explore the potential of a Kitchen Guide concept was the interviews conducted individually with each family after the demo-phase. We went around all 20 homes and interviewed the inhabitants based on a previously prepared interview guide. The interviews show two helpful perspectives on end-user value: one with *added value* to direct the inquiry, while the other relates to understanding the field material toward design (see figure 3).

Figure 3: Snapshots of different interview situations, with the whole family present, engaged talking and discussing the probes.

The interview design was inspired by a marketing perspective with its first part to explore wants and needs a Kitchen Guide could satisfy, then addressing questions around the marketing mix factors. We however went beyond this notion to seek new opportunities for design by keeping an open interview style throughout and challenge the informants on their answers. Thereby the road-map of interview topics ranged from the usability of the given prototype’s functions, their potential and the overall concept to addressing related attitudes, potential use-situations, everyday practice and thereby eventually directly or indirectly values – increasing abstraction as we went along. So the interviews included both the notion of *evaluation*, as in determining the fixed value of something (Merriam-Webster, 15.05.2008), and a more reflexive and relational notion of value. If they for example brought up a specific design requirement, we would question it to discuss use-situations and everyday life in order to understand the essence behind what they were saying. In several cases the first positive reaction on a design feature, was withdrawn as he or she further reflected on how they actually do things in their everyday. What they do in a way reflects, who they are – toward identities and values. For instance the evaluating questions on the design’s food magnification function, through openness in the interview structure and additional, dynamic questioning revealed a strong interest of families with children

to provide a varied, interesting diet and educate them for healthy living. So in relation to higher, more abstract values, parents care for their children and love them. They could see this as a promising design direction. That parents care for their children is not a surprise as such, yet given that these value expressions have derived in relation to specific design attributes and are elicited in relation to the kitchen context make the conclusion worth-while – it is specifically about the kitchen, food, diet, learning, sharing and caring for each other. As expected it became clear that the prototype had caused quite a lot of frustrations, as it did not live up to a functional product. The families however were able to set aside that fact and provide rich and useful insights for the project team.

Customer or user research?

Along the lines of involving users in the design process and how this interplays with an end-user value focus, two main questions remain. How can marketing inspired benefit-thinking strengthen a user-centered design process? Can and should we embed values in a design solution? While marketing research as well suggests acquiring knowledge in the real world context, it is more concerned with “field experiments that are conducted externally in market environments” (Crimp, Wright, 1995, p. 93). The user-driven perspective extends this notion. We look to generate as rich information from the users as possible, while marketing techniques at times may only scratch the surface. In this example we used the benefit-thinking from marketing to inspire the interview design, while keeping the empathetic and design-inspired approach to inquiry. This differentiates our approach from the business world’s in two main points: (1) We took a relational approach to *evaluating* the design concept characterized by: longer term involvement, several touch points of researchers and users, a variation of interdependent techniques, personal and empathetic inquiry style, context-situated interviewing. (2) The inquiry was design-focused and utilized a supposedly limited prototype as an effective provocation to gather feedback on the design concept and conclude on promising design directions. Consumer behavior studies for instance do suggest how to ask into values by starting in the lowest level of the value hierarchy that related to functional attributes (Woodruff, Gardial, 1996). This requires a product to be there to start with. We however had a conceptual design at a prototype-in-development level, which demanded a different strategy of inquiry.

As this shows, it is well possible to couple the two approaches to provide fruitful insights for the design process. This moreover partly derived from having prepared and challenged the families to reflect on their daily practice in the kitchen through a combination of introductory meetings, a physical probes package with tasks and questions and the prototype itself – all stressing the fact that we were not providing a finished product solution, though the official phrasing ‘a prototype

to test for 2 months' may imply so. This speaks for the importance of an empathetic approach to inquiry in the early stages of product development, while the different views on value can be useful. Tailoring the inquiry to find out what *added value* the users could get through the product allowed to bring *values of the families* to the surface as they related to everyday life in and around their kitchen. One could therefore think that we could design for those values, somehow embedding them in our design. However the fluid notion of values suggests other. Just as values and identities constantly change in a specific context, unexpected use of products cannot be fully avoided. A value perspective, as implied in the users stories from everyday practice, may however be useful to avoid the tendency to focus on pure usability, and can help address qualities beyond that. On the other hand designing for end-user value bears the danger of forgetting about the specific context. For the kitchen context this is for instance the need of effectiveness in everyday cooking, while a more general family value may be that they want to spend time together. These contrasting insights need to be balanced in a nuanced look upon what this means for design and, in return, how design will affect these. Here *value* in the light of constructed identities allows incorporating the fluid notion, which automatically includes the specific context. In this way we as designers can take conscious decisions to which degree we are designing to fit, or change or even provoke everyday practice.

In summary the fluid notion of values is contradicting to attempts of designing for specific values. Just as values and identities change in a specific context, unexpected use of products cannot be avoided. Yet, as the case shows, the *added value* perspective can work to reduce complexity, ease communication and to elicit interesting design directions. Eventually this mixed-method approach allowed to bridge disciplines within the course of the design process.

Values-in-action to guide design practice

What the Kitchen Guide project lacks is an interesting interaction design outcome. The components of the physical interfaces were predetermined (laptop with keyboard and mouse, scanner, web-interface) and thereby narrowed in-how-far interaction could be explored and designed. Moreover time restrains further limited the possibilities to explore this direction. To cover the design side better I briefly discuss two concept examples of student projects, redesigning the microwave oven.

Emphasis on interaction – A snapshot of two innovative microwave ovens

Tada: A social microwave oven concept.

The *Tada* microwave oven is mounted in the center of the table, with access from multiple angles. The rounded dining-platter-like lid is removed and several dishes, or different kinds of

food can be placed inside on multiple levels. The heat level is determined by rotating the lid according to projected color indicators on the table. With these main design attributes the students managed to challenge how we use and perceive a microwave. Moreover it became clear that this concept, put into use, would change the way we cook together; microwave cooking as socially engaging. Various use scenarios were employed in the project to build a consciousness of the possible implications the design would have in people's everyday life (see figure 4). (Kilbourn, 2005)

Figure 4: The students at out use scenarios with the mock-up of the *Tada*.

SpinTop: An action-oriented microwave oven concept.

The *SpinTop* mainly explores how interaction design can exploit human actions and movements to enhance use experience. It provides a variety of interaction styles to set different heat and time preferences. As an option the microwave allows the users to determine which actions should initiate which heating program. Thereby designing an element of freedom for expression into the interaction possibilities, which is assumed could lead to a richer and skillful heating activity (see figure 5). (Moser, 2008)

Figure 5: Different styles of interacting with the *SpinTop*.

In summary the *Tada* serves as an example to further stress how design may impact everyday practice, hence interaction design influences not only how we interact with product, but also with each other. Buur and Ylirisku as well stress that “Design fundamentally is about facilitating change: the design team may want to change products, systems and services and through this they will inevitably change the practice of the people using them.” (Buur & Ylirisku, 2007, p.191). The *SpinTop* concept addresses how a) values can be directly perceived through the interaction qualities themselves (e.g. the shaking action *feels* good and thereby impacts the user on the emotional level) and b) values can be an outcome of interaction (e.g. shaking the microwave hardly determines the heat level, hence energy consumption. In this way users would *feel* the energy and possibly become more aware of energy consumption in general, through which they could associate to environmental concerns, global warming, saving the world etc.).

Discussion

Looking at the three cases together, they were all initiated with unique underlying assumptions on what design direction is interesting to explore, carried out with a specific set of methods, deliver a unique design concept and thereby contribute in distinct ways to the discussion of end-user value for design. They however commonly agree on the desire and ambition to contribute in generating innovative and human-centered designs. The *values-in-action* notion seems to well summarize this into an actionable mind-set for design practice and puts forward the importance of linking design to end-user values. As table 1 illustrates, the *Kitchen Guide* prototyping project, the *Tada* and *SpinTop* microwave oven concepts highlight different aspects on the discussion of end-user values in design. The *SpinTop* emphasizes that the interaction design, as exploiting human actions and movements, can be a direct way to input value for users that taps

into or changes people's values. Depending on the latter, people's perception of the value they gain from interaction is as well determined – a fluid relational notion. The *Tada* serves as an effective example to demonstrate how interaction design can fundamentally impact everyday life. The case illustrates the potential to completely change how we generally engage socially and cook together. In contrast to the two microwave projects, the *Kitchen Guide* prototyping project does not propose a final design concept. The project serves as an example of a mixed-methods approach that introduces the notion of *added value* to bridge disciplinary practice. This was utilized in ways of talking and doing (internal project world and actual engagement with families).

	Starting with a design brief - Which underlying assumptions ?	Getting done - What kind of product ?	Relating to the users - Which methods ?	Reflecting - What contribution to the value discussion ?
<p>KITCHEN GUIDE</p>	<p>Conceptual design</p> <p>Exploration of RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) technology's potential in relation to food and the home context.</p>	<p>Functionality: system to access information/service on specific foods in the home.</p> <p>Components: laptop, via USB-cable attached scanner, web-application.</p> <p>Interaction: finger-pointing, push, grab & swing-by (food), one-angle access.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - User workshop - Kitchen probes - Family interviews - Questionnaire - Online blog <p>(about 1 year project)</p>	<p>Example of a mixed-method approach, based on the notion of value, in a user-centred design inspired project.</p> <p>Value notion made explicit in methods to bridge multi-disciplinary teamwork.</p>
<p>TADA</p>	<p>Redesign of microwave oven</p> <p>Exploration of socially engaging design.</p> <p>Exploit interaction possibilities.</p>	<p>Functionality: Quickly heat up/ cook food and engage with others.</p> <p>Components: mounted in table, lid with digital timer, handles, knob, colour range projection.</p> <p>Interaction: grab & turn (handles), grab & lift (lid), multiple-angles access.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - historical analysis of interaction styles in the kitchen - use scenarios - puppet scenarios (based on cooking scenario from the field) <p>(Buur, & Yirisku, 2007, p.127, pp.156-157 & pp. 165-168)</p> <p>(two-week project)</p>	<p>Example of interaction design concept that challenges the idea of design consciously changing everyday practice, hence also our values.</p> <p>Value notion implicit in trying to understand how we are affected by design - here specifically designing for sociality.</p>
<p>SPIN TOP</p>	<p>Redesign of microwave oven</p> <p>Exploration of kitchens as action environments needing action technology (challenge IT, information-focussed paradigm).</p> <p>Exploit interaction possibilities.</p>	<p>Functionality: Quickly heat up/ cook food and support action notion.</p> <p>Components: bowl-shaped container with top load lid, surrounding handles, anchored in base.</p> <p>Interaction: spin, sway, press & shake, rock-slow, rock-fast, multiple-angles</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - video analysis (cooking observations from field studies) - use scenarios <p>(three-week project)</p>	<p>Example of interaction design concept that challenges us to think specific interaction properties and values in relation to each other.</p> <p>Value notion implicit in, moving beyond usability and connecting the physical world of interaction with interfaces to a higher level of values.</p>

Table 1: Overview of the design cases' starting points, process and outcome, as well as their contributions to the discussion of the value notion for interaction design.

Conclusion

In this paper I provide a conceptual contribution to a discussion on end-user values, set out in a theoretical discussion contrasting a business and social constructivist perspective. I put forward *added value* as a means to analyze what design can contribute to everyday life quality. This can help bridge the multidisciplinary collaboration needed to develop innovative design concepts, specifically between business and design-oriented thinkers. The two microwave design concepts support the idea that values actually in some way can be *designed into* a product. The examples highlight the importance of context further and emphasize how specific interaction design correlates with end-user values. Based on the investigations here, I propose that a *values-in-*

action notion, as a specific approach to end-user values, can contribute to design practice in two main ways: (1) on a methods level in the earlier development phases (a mixed-methods approach) and (2) determining interaction design details toward the final design. Altogether, working with this notion of *values-in-action*, we may achieve that the business partners understand better, acknowledge and engage more freely in user-centered design processes. At the same time we ensure that we consciously deal with the terms value and values and utilize this to estimate the consequences our designs really may have on people's lives.

Acknowledgements

Many thanks to the families and consortium involved in the Kitchen Guide project and research assistants, Anne Museus, Ida Rasmussen and Mark Asboe, the professor in social psychology, Lasse Dencik and the IT Product Design students, Kyle Kilbourne, Sarah Hardung, Jan Hoefnagels and Shirley Bi (*Tada*), and Shiran Moser, Zheng Dai, Kaare Holm Warming and Emanuela Marchetti (*SpinTop*), who came up with the microwave oven concepts.

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